

INFLUENCES OF INTRINSIC AND EXTRINSIC MOTIVATIONS: ENHANCING STUDENTS' ENGAGEMENT IN ASYNCHRONOUS ACTIVITIES IN ARLING PANLIPUNAN

MICHELLE ANN L. CASTILLO, LPT

michelleanncastillo63@gmail.com

0000-0002-5464-611X

Laguna State Polytechnic University –San Pablo Campus

ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to determine the level of students' intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivations in asynchronous activities in Araling Panlipunan. It was also intended to correlate students' motivations to their participation and satisfaction. The study utilized descriptive correlational method of research. It involved 45 purposively selected grade 9 students under online distance modality of Palo Alto Integrated School during the academic year 2020-2021. Survey-questionnaires were distributed and answered by the students using google forms. Results revealed that in terms of interest or enjoyment, perceived competence and perceived choice, there is a significant relationship between students' intrinsic motivation and their participation and satisfaction in asynchronous activities. Furthermore, it was discovered that in terms of external, introjected, identified and integrated regulation, there is a significant relationship between students' extrinsic motivation and their participation and satisfaction. However, it was revealed that there is no significant relationship between students' intrinsic motivations in terms of pressure or tension and their participation and satisfaction. Based on the findings, it was recommended for the school to conduct programs, online seminars and trainings for teachers who are handling online distance learners. These seminars should focus on strategies and approaches to improve their students' motivation and engagement. It was also suggested for online teachers to use motivational and holistic activities in giving asynchronous activities especially in Araling Panlipunan.

Keywords: psychology, motivation, descriptive, Philippines